

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET

Dr. Henry Garrett ◦ Independent Researcher ◦ Department of Mathematics ◦ DrHenryGarrett@gmail.com ◦ Manhattan, NY, USA

1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\ & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\ & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\ & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\ & \} \}. \end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and a Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD

DOMINATING SET. Since there are more ways to get type results a Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. “values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, “Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, “values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, “super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET until Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, then it is officially called “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”, but otherwise, it is not Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Because of having Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET” and “neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET is redefined to a “Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is

given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET or the strongest Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET called Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and the strongest Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET called Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis

about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neurosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET or Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET” and “neutrosophic Strongly

EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, are specified in the sections “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET” and “Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”. In the concept of dealing with results and in Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”, “Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [1],Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [1],Definition

2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [1].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$^-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x), I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]-0, 1^+[$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.2,p.2).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.5,p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

(i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;

- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$\text{and } F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $I'_V(E_{i'})$, and $F'_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 2. TThe Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there is only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . 298
299
300
301
- On the Figure (4), there is no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 is a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$. 302
303
304
- On the Figure (5), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 305
306
- On the Figure (6), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 307
308
- On the Figure (7), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 309
310

Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModelling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (8), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 311
312
- On the Figure (9), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 313
314
- On the Figure (10), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 315
316
- On the Figure (11), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 317
318
- On the Figure (12), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 319
320
- On the Figure (13), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 321
322
- On the Figure (14), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 323
324
- On the Figure (15), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 325
326
- On the Figure (16), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 327
328
- On the Figure (17), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 329
330
- On the Figure (18), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 331
332
- On the Figure (19), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 333
334

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 16. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-overpacked SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (20), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 335
336
- On the Figure (21), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 337
338
- On the Figure (22), there's neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 339
340

Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 341
(Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 342

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 343
344
345
346

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 347
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 348
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 349
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 350
351
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 352
353
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 354
355

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 356
357

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$:

(i) $1 \otimes x = x$;

(ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$;

(iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$;

(iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$.

Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$\text{and } F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$supp(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

(i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;

(ii) $V = \{ (V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0 \}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;

(iv) $E = \{ (E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0 \}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);

(vii) $\sum_i supp(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);

(viii) $\sum_{i'} supp(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).
(Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESHP : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion.

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 28. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.20)

SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;

(iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;

(iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** .

Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

(i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;

(ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;

(iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$;

(iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\})_{i=1}^s$.

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called

(ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;

(x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;

(xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$;

(xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to “**redefine**” the notion of “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds.

It's useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable.

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar, Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite, and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds.

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5). 531
532
- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6). 533
534
- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7). 535
536

4 Main Resultant 537

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET). 538
539

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds. 540
541
542
543
544

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\
 & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 36. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 37. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 38. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 39. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 40. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 41. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} = \\
 & \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\
 & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} = \\
 & \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) \mid \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

if every vertex in set D is adjacent to
 equally number of vertices in $V - D$
 }|.

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10). 561
562

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds. 563
564
565
566
567

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} = \\
 & \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\
 & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11). 568
569

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds. 570
571
572
573
574

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} =
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.19, 0.19, 0.19)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

$$\min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right.$$

if every vertex in set D is adjacent to
equally number of vertices in $V - D$

$$\left. \right\}.$$

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12). 575
576

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds. 577
578
579
580
581

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

$$= \text{NOT DEFINED} =$$

$$\min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right.$$

if every vertex in set D is adjacent to
equally number of vertices in $V - D$

$$\left. \right\}.$$

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13). 582
583

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds. 584
585
586
587
588

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

= NOT DEFINED =

$$\min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right.$$

if every vertex in set D is adjacent to
equally number of vertices in $V - D$

$$\left. \right\} \mid.$$

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=2}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right.$$

if every vertex in set D is adjacent to
equally number of vertices in $V - D$

$$\left. \right\} \mid.$$

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{\text{NOT DEFINED}}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} = \\
 & \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\
 & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} = \\
 & \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |\{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\
 & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17).

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} = \\
 & \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\
 & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \text{NOT DEFINED} = \\
 & \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} | \{ (\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i)) | \\
 & \text{if every vertex in set } D \text{ is adjacent to} \\
 & \text{equally number of vertices in } V - D \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_5	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)
V_6	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)	V_7	(0.23, 0.23, 0.23)

= NOT DEFINED =

$$\min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right.$$

if every vertex in set D is adjacent to
equally number of vertices in $V - D$

$$\left. \right\} \left. \right|.$$

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}$ NOT DEFINED. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperEQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET criteria holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

= NOT DEFINED =

$$\min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \mid \right. \right.$$

if every vertex in set D is adjacent to
equally number of vertices in $V - D$

$$\left. \right\} \left. \right|.$$

5 Main Result

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem).

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel coincides.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET number is as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET number is as follows.*

$$0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2 \end{aligned}$$

$$P :$$

$$E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel**.

Proposition 5.7. Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET set is as follows.

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.8. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET number is lower than as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET set is as follows.*

$$\{CENTER\}.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1,$$

CENTER, E_2

749

$P :$
 $E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL},$
 $E_2, CENTER$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

750

751

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

752

753

754

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET number is lower than as follows.*

0.26.

Proof. Let

755

$P :$
 $V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1,$
 $CENTER, E_2$

756

$P :$
 $E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL},$
 $E_2, CENTER$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

757

758

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

759

760

761

Proposition 5.11. *(Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel).*

762

763

- (i). *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET set.*

764

765

766

767

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic CENTER has the letter maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.12. (*Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar*). 794
795

(i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then *CENTER* is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar^{Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET} set. 796
797

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then *CENTER* is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar^{Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET} set. 798
799
800

Proof. 801

(i). Let 802

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1, \\ CENTER, E_2$$
803

$$P : \\ E_1, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2, CENTER$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 804
805

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar^{Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET}. The latter is straightforward. 806
807
808

(ii). Let 809

$$P : \\ V_1^{EXTERNAL}, E_1^*, \\ CENTER, E_2^*$$
810

$$P : \\ E_1^*, V_1^{EXTERNAL}, \\ E_2^*, CENTER$$

is a longest SuperHyperStar^{Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET} taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperWheel $ESHW : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as 811
812
813

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar^{Strongly} 814
815

EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. ◻

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region has been assigned by the Neutrosophic model [it's called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] and the long Neutrosophic cycle of the move from the cancer is identified by this research. Sometimes the move of the cancer hasn't be easily identified since there are some determinacy, indeterminacy and neutrality about the moves and the effects of the cancer on that region; this event leads us to choose another model [it's said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph] to have convenient perception on what's happened and what's done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models, which are well-known and they've got the names, and some general Neutrosophic models. The moves and the Neutrosophic traces of the cancer on the complex tracks and between complicated groups of cells could be fantasized by a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath(-/SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The aim is to find either the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET or the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET in those Neutrosophic Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels.

7 Case 1: The Initial Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (42) and the Table (21), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite is obtained.

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (42), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET.

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (43), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. By using the Neutrosophic Figure (43) and the Table (22), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (43), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET.

Figure 43. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET

Table 22. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

9 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

Cancer is a neutrosophic disease, but the neutrosophic model is supposed to understand what is going on in this neutrosophic phenomenon. The special case of neutrosophic disease is considered and some parameters have been used as consequences of the model. Cells are subject to attack by the disease, but the movements of the cancer in the specific area is a matter of mind. Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer can help in finding some Neutrosophic cures for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, several Neutrosophic stages are designed for this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) Neutrosophic diagnosis of cancer in long-term Neutrosophic performance.

Step 2. (Neutrosophic Issue) The specific region is assigned by the Neutrosophic model (called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph) and the long Neutrosophic cycle of movement of cancer is identified by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done.

Step 3. (Neutrosophic Model) There are some specific Neutrosophic models that are well known and have names and some general Neutrosophic models. Cancer neutrosophic movements and effects in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find dominant neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET models or dominant sStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET models.

10 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 10.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 10.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET?*

Question 10.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 10.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET?*

Problem 10.5. *The SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer's recognitions and they're based on SuperHyperStrongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, are there else?*

Problem 10.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 10.7. *What's the independent research based on Cancer's recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

11 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title "Cancer Diagnosis". To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in the Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET and Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in "cancer diagnosis" and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called "Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET", based on the connections of Cancer's movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The "SuperHyper" prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In the table (23), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

12 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot" in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with

Table 23. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	
2. Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET	
3. Neutrosophic Strongly EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET	2.
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	

introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*" with ISO abbreviation "*Curr Trends Mass Comm*" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments*" in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer's Treatments. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*A Research on Cancer's Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*" in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer's Recognition. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*" in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Math Techniques Comput Math*" in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by*

Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*” with ISO abbreviation “*IJPAMR*” in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*” with ISO abbreviation “*IJPAMR*” in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages 242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs*” in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled “*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs*” in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*” in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Neutrosophic Version Of*

Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer's Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer's Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph" in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer's Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer's Circumstances Where Cancer's Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints" in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond" in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer's Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints" in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints" in **Ref. [23]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances" in **Ref. [24]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses" in **Ref. [25]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer's Recognitions" in **Ref. [26]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments" in **Ref. [27]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses" in **Ref. [28]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer's Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [294]** by Henry Garrett (2023), "The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer's Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [295]** by Henry Garrett (2023), "Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer's Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer's Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [296]** by Henry Garrett (2023), "Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer's Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer's Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs" in **Ref. [297]** by Henry Garrett (2023), "Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding

Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in **Ref. [300]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*” in **Ref. [301]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [304]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [307]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*” in **Ref. [308]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [309]** by Henry Garrett (2023), “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*” in **Ref. [310]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [311]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*” in **Ref. [312]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*” in **Ref. [323]** by Henry Garrett (2022), “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*” in **Ref. [324]** by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4–324], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [325–483]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [484, 485].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [484]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref. [485]** by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It’s titled “*Neutrosophic Duality*” and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It’s smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what’s done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1–3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4–324] alongside scientific research books at [325–483]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd ,in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [484, 485].

References

1. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot”, *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03). 1163
1164
1165
1166
2. Henry Garrett, “Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05). 1167
1168
1169
1170
3. Henry Garrett, “A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03). 1171
1172
1173
1174
4. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04). 1175
1176
1177
1178
5. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88). 1179
1180
1181
1182
6. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124). 1183
1184
1185
1186
7. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut”, *J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res* 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04) 1187
1188
1189
1190
8. Henry Garrett, “Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes”, *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 1191
1192
1193
1194
9. Garrett, Henry. “0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>.
<https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 1195
1196
1197
1198
1199
1200
10. Garrett, Henry. “0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>.
<https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1201
1202
1203
1204
1205
11. Henry Garrett, “Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of 1206
1207

- (*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1208
1209
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1210
1211
1212
1213
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 1214
1215
1216
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1217
1218
1219
1220
1221
1222
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1223
1224
1225
1226
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1227
1228
1229
1230
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1231
1232
1233
1234
18. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1235
1236
1237
19. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1238
1239
1240
1241
20. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1242
1243
1244
21. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1245
1246
1247
22. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1248
1249
1250
1251

23. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1252-1255
24. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 1256-1258
25. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 1259-1263
26. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 1264-1266
27. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 1267-1270
28. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 1271-1274
29. Henry Garrett, “*Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices*”, Preprints 2024, , 2024020663 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.0663.v1). 1275-1278
30. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14552432). 1279-1281
31. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14547873). 1282-1284
32. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14543895). 1285-1288
33. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14540759). 1289-1291
34. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14536608). 1292-1294
35. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION*”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14527040). 1295-1297

36. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By ESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14515147). 1298
1299
1300
37. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By ESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14507321). 1301
1302
1303
38. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By RESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14501230). 1304
1305
1306
39. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14477108). 1307
1308
1309
40. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14449513). 1310
1311
1312
41. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14261015). 1313
1314
1315
42. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14031032). 1316
1317
1318
43. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14019047). 1319
1320
1321
44. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13957693). 1322
1323
1324
45. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13909326). 1325
1326
1327
46. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13893734). 1328
1329
1330
47. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13890872). 1331
1332
1333
48. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13834065). 1334
1335
1336
49. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13826744). 1337
1338
1339
50. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13823150). 1340
1341
1342

51. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13748678). 1343
1344
1345
52. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13629264). 1346
1347
1348
53. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13618512). 1349
1350
1351
54. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13457634). 1352
1353
1354
55. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13447621). 1355
1356
1357
56. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13386125). 1358
1359
1360
57. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359880). 1361
1362
1363
58. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359103). 1364
1365
1366
59. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13329472). 1367
1368
1369
60. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13091499). 1370
1371
1372
61. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13134329). 1373
1374
1375
62. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13218489). 1376
1377
1378
63. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Zero Forcing From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12788786). 1379
1380
1381
64. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12752339). 1382
1383
1384
65. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12738172). 1385
1386
1387

66. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12680424). 1388
1389
1390
67. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12675758). 1391
1392
1393
68. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12656919). 1394
1395
1396
69. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12576337). 1397
1398
1399
70. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12556338). 1400
1401
1402
71. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12536399). 1403
1404
1405
72. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12174846). 1406
1407
1408
73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12129978). 1409
1410
1411
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12024191). 1412
1413
1414
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11661528). 1415
1416
1417
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11651866). 1418
1419
1420
77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11634496). 1421
1422
1423
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11513482). 1424
1425
1426
79. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11479559). 1427
1428
1429
80. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11438586). 1430
1431
1432

81. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11253553). 1433
1434
1435
82. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11218489). 1436
1437
1438
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11169069). 1439
1440
1441
84. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075522). 1442
1443
1444
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10982844). 1445
1446
1447
86. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10963312). 1448
1449
1450
87. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10929590). 1451
1452
1453
88. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10918770). 1454
1455
1456
89. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10910154). 1457
1458
1459
90. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899659). 1460
1461
1462
91. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10895887). 1463
1464
1465
92. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10888691). 1466
1467
1468
93. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10851065). 1469
1470
1471
1472
94. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10796076). 1473
1474
1475
1476

95. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Multipartite and Counteroffer Cycle By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10640905). 1477
1478
1479
1480
96. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769). 1481
1482
1483
1484
97. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727). 1485
1486
1487
1488
98. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169). 1489
1490
1491
1492
99. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529). 1493
1494
1495
100. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535). 1496
1497
1498
101. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440). 1499
1500
1501
1502
102. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600). 1503
1504
1505
103. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454). 1506
1507
1508
104. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1). 1509
1510
1511
105. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182). 1512
1513
1514
106. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877). 1515
1516
1517
1518
107. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834). 1519
1520
1521
1522

108. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773). 1523
1524
1525
1526
109. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319). 1527
1528
1529
1530
110. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255). 1531
1532
1533
1534
111. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1535
1536
1537
1538
112. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1539
1540
1541
1542
113. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1543
1544
1545
1546
114. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1547
1548
1549
1550
115. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1551
1552
1553
116. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1554
1555
1556
117. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1557
1558
1559
118. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1560
1561
1562
119. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1563
1564
1565
120. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1566
1567
1568

121. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1569
1570
1571
122. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1572
1573
1574
123. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1575
1576
1577
124. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1578
1579
1580
125. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1581
1582
1583
126. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1584
1585
1586
127. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1587
1588
1589
128. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1590
1591
1592
129. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1593
1594
1595
130. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1596
1597
1598
131. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1599
1600
1601
132. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1602
1603
1604
133. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1605
1606
1607
134. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1608
1609
1610
135. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1611
1612
1613

136. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1614
1615
1616
137. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1617
1618
1619
138. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1620
1621
1622
139. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1623
1624
1625
140. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1626
1627
1628
141. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1629
1630
1631
142. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1632
1633
1634
143. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1635
1636
1637
144. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1638
1639
1640
145. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1641
1642
1643
146. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1644
1645
1646
147. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1647
1648
1649
148. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1650
1651
1652
149. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1653
1654
1655
150. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1656
1657
1658

151. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1659
1660
1661
152. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1662
1663
1664
153. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1665
1666
1667
154. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1668
1669
1670
155. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1671
1672
1673
156. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1674
1675
1676
1677
157. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1678
1679
1680
1681
158. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1682
1683
1684
159. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1685
1686
1687
160. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1688
1689
1690
161. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1691
1692
1693
162. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1694
1695
1696
163. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1697
1698
1699
164. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1700
1701
1702

165. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1703
1704
1705
166. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1706
1707
1708
167. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1709
1710
1711
168. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1712
1713
1714
169. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1715
1716
1717
170. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1718
1719
1720
171. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1721
1722
1723
172. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1724
1725
1726
173. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1727
1728
1729
174. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1730
1731
1732
175. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1733
1734
1735
176. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1736
1737
1738
177. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1739
1740
1741
178. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1742
1743
1744
179. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1745
1746
1747

180. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1748
1749
1750
181. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1751
1752
1753
182. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1754
1755
1756
183. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238). 1757
1758
1759
1760
184. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228). 1761
1762
1763
185. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902). 1764
1765
1766
186. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218). 1767
1768
1769
187. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334). 1770
1771
1772
188. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372). 1773
1774
1775
189. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952). 1776
1777
1778
190. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982). 1779
1780
1781
191. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026). 1782
1783
1784
192. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052). 1785
1786
1787
193. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066). 1788
1789
1790

194. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094). 1791
1792
1793
195. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476). 1794
1795
1796
196. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082). 1797
1798
1799
197. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1800
1801
1802
198. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1803
1804
1805
199. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1806
1807
1808
200. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1809
1810
1811
201. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1812
1813
1814
202. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1815
1816
1817
203. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1818
1819
1820
204. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1821
1822
1823
205. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1824
1825
1826
206. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1827
1828
1829
207. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1830
1831
1832
208. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1833
1834
1835

209. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1836
1837
1838
210. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1839
1840
1841
211. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decompenation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1842
1843
1844
212. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decompenation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1845
1846
1847
213. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1848
1849
1850
214. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1851
1852
1853
215. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1854
1855
1856
216. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1857
1858
1859
217. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1860
1861
1862
218. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1863
1864
1865
219. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1866
1867
1868
220. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1869
1870
1871
221. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1872
1873
1874
222. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1875
1876
1877
223. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1878
1879
1880

224. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1881
1882
1883
225. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 1884
1885
1886
226. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 1887
1888
1889
227. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 1890
1891
1892
228. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 1893
1894
1895
229. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 1896
1897
1898
230. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 1899
1900
1901
231. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 1902
1903
1904
232. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 1905
1906
1907
233. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 1908
1909
1910
234. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 1911
1912
1913
235. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 1914
1915
1916
236. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 1917
1918
1919
237. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 1920
1921
1922
238. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 1923
1924
1925

239. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 1926
1927
1928
240. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 1929
1930
1931
241. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 1932
1933
1934
242. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 1935
1936
1937
243. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 1938
1939
1940
244. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 1941
1942
1943
245. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 1944
1945
1946
246. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 1947
1948
1949
247. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 1950
1951
1952
248. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 1953
1954
1955
249. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 1956
1957
1958
250. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 1959
1960
1961
251. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 1962
1963
1964
252. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 1965
1966
1967
253. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 1968
1969
1970

254. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 1971
1972
1973
255. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 1974
1975
1976
256. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 1977
1978
1979
257. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 1980
1981
1982
258. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 1983
1984
1985
259. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 1986
1987
1988
260. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 1989
1990
1991
261. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 1992
1993
1994
262. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 1995
1996
1997
263. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 1998
1999
2000
264. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 2001
2002
2003
265. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 2004
2005
2006
266. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 2007
2008
2009
267. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 2010
2011
2012
268. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 2013
2014
2015

269. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 2016
2017
2018
270. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 2019
2020
2021
271. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 2022
2023
2024
2025
272. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 2026
2027
2028
2029
273. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 2030
2031
2032
2033
274. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 2034
2035
2036
2037
275. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 2038
2039
2040
2041
276. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 2042
2043
2044
2045
277. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 2046
2047
2048
2049
278. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 2050
2051
2052
279. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 2053
2054
2055
280. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 2056
2057
2058

281. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 2059
2060
2061
2062
282. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 2063
2064
2065
2066
283. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 2067
2068
2069
2070
2071
284. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 2072
2073
2074
2075
2076
285. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 2077
2078
2079
2080
286. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 2081
2082
2083
287. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 2084
2085
2086
2087
288. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 2088
2089
2090
2091
289. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 2092
2093
2094
290. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 2095
2096
2097
2098
2099
2100
291. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 2101
2102
2103
2104

292. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 2105
2106
2107
2108
293. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 2109
2110
2111
2112
294. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 2113
2114
2115
295. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 2116
2117
2118
2119
296. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2120
2121
2122
2123
297. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 2124
2125
2126
2127
298. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2128
2129
2130
2131
299. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2132
2133
2134
300. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 2135
2136
2137
301. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 2138
2139
2140
2141
302. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2142
2143
2144
2145
303. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 2146
2147
2148
2149

304. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 2150
2151
2152
2153
305. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 2154
2155
2156
306. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 2157
2158
2159
307. Henry Garrett, “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 2160
2161
2162
308. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 2163
2164
2165
309. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 2166
2167
2168
310. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 2169
2170
2171
2172
311. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 2173
2174
2175
312. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 2176
2177
2178
2179
313. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 2180
2181
2182
314. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 2183
2184
2185
315. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 2186
2187
2188
2189
2190
316. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 2191
2192
2193
2194
2195

317. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 2196
2197
2198
318. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 2199
2200
2201
319. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 2202
2203
2204
2205
320. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 2206
2207
2208
2209
321. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 2210
2211
2212
2213
322. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 2214
2215
2216
2217
323. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 2218
2219
2220
324. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 2221
2222
2223
2224
325. Henry Garrett, ”STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14544008). 2225
2226
326. Henry Garrett, ”DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14527741). 2227
2228
327. Henry Garrett, ”RESTRAINED DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14497269). 2229
2230
328. Henry Garrett, ”Dom-forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14175736). 2231
2232
329. Henry Garrett, ”Diamond search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13600433). 2233
2234
330. Henry Garrett, ”Triangle-free search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13594674). 2235
2236
331. Henry Garrett, ”Diamond search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13525750). 2237
2238

332. Henry Garrett, "Triangle-free search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13512157). 2239
2240
333. Henry Garrett, "Edge Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13376543). 2241
2242
334. Henry Garrett, "Vertex Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13294466). 2243
2244
335. Henry Garrett, "Burning Number In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12797511). 2245
2246
336. Henry Garrett, "Zero Forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12691570). 2247
2248
337. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 6". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12651785). 2249
2250
338. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 5". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12214087). 2251
2252
339. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 4". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11876996). 2253
2254
340. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11529821). 2255
2256
341. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11398118). 2257
2258
342. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 1". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11106891). 2259
2260
343. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10946745). 2261
2262
344. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10909931). 2263
2264
345. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10871136). 2265
2266
346. Henry Garrett, "Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 2267
2268
347. Henry Garrett, "Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 2269
2270
348. Henry Garrett, "Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 2271
2272
349. Henry Garrett, "Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 2273
2274
350. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 2275
2276
351. Henry Garrett, "Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 2277
2278

352. Henry Garrett, “Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 2279
2280
353. Henry Garrett, “Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 2281
2282
354. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 2283
2284
355. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 2285
2286
356. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 2287
2288
357. Henry Garrett, “Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 2289
2290
358. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 2291
2292
359. Henry Garrett, “Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 2293
2294
360. Henry Garrett, “Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 2295
2296
361. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 2297
2298
362. Henry Garrett, “Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 2299
2300
363. Henry Garrett, “Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 2301
2302
364. Henry Garrett, “Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 2303
2304
365. Henry Garrett, “Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 2305
2306
366. Henry Garrett, “Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 2307
2308
367. Henry Garrett, “United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2309
2310
368. Henry Garrett, “Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2311
2312
369. Henry Garrett, “Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2313
2314
370. Henry Garrett, “Collections of Math II”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2315
2316
371. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2317
2318

372. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2319
2320
373. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2321
2322
374. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2323
2324
375. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2325
2326
376. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2327
2328
377. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2329
2330
378. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2331
2332
379. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2333
2334
380. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2335
2336
381. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2337
2338
382. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2339
2340
383. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2341
2342
384. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2343
2344
385. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2345
2346
386. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2347
2348
387. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2349
2350
388. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2351
2352
389. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2353
2354
390. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2355
2356
391. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2357
2358

392. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2359
2360
393. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2361
2362
394. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2363
2364
395. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2365
2366
396. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2367
2368
397. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2369
2370
398. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2371
2372
399. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2373
2374
400. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2375
2376
401. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995) . 2377
2378
402. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2379
2380
403. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2381
2382
404. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2383
2384
405. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2385
2386
406. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2387
2388
407. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2389
2390
408. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2391
2392
409. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2393
2394
410. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2395
2396
411. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2397
2398

412. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2399
2400
413. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2401
2402
414. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2403
2404
415. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2405
2406
416. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2407
2408
417. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2409
2410
418. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2411
2412
419. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2413
2414
420. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2415
2416
421. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2417
2418
422. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2419
2420
423. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2421
2422
424. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2423
2424
425. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2425
2426
426. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2427
2428
427. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2429
2430
428. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2431
2432
429. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2433
2434
430. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2435
2436
431. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2437
2438

- 432. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2439
2440
- 433. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2441
2442
- 434. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2443
2444
- 435. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2445
2446
- 436. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2447
2448
- 437. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2449
2450
- 438. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2451
2452
- 439. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2453
2454
- 440. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2455
2456
- 441. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2457
2458
- 442. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2459
2460
- 443. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2461
2462
- 444. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2463
2464
- 445. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2465
2466
- 446. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2467
2468
- 447. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2469
2470
- 448. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2471
2472
- 449. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2473
2474
- 450. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2475
2476
- 451. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2477
2478

452. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2479
2480
453. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2481
2482
454. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2483
2484
455. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2485
2486
456. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2487
2488
457. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2489
2490
458. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2491
2492
459. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2493
2494
460. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2495
2496
461. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2497
2498
462. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2499
2500
463. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2501
2502
464. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2503
2504
465. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2505
2506
466. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2507
2508
467. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2509
2510
468. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2511
2512
469. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2513
2514
470. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2515
2516
471. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2517
2518

472. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2519
2520
473. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2521
2522
474. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2523
2524
475. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2525
2526
476. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2527
2528
477. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2529
2530
478. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2531
2532
479. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2533
2534
480. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2535
2536
481. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2537
2538
482. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2539
2540
483. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2541
2542
484. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2543
2544
485. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2545
2546